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Cross-fertilisation: A dialogue aid for SSH and STEM researchers

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Social Sciences & Humanities for Climate,
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Introduction

How can I use this infographic and who is the audience?

This infographic aims to help you understand diverse perspectives and have discussions about navigating interdisciplinary challenges. It serves as a tool for researchers from both SSH and STEM backgrounds, facilitating conversations from various viewpoints. These diverse perspectives enrich research design and approaches, but can also present challenges, such as differing definitions of core concepts, language barriers, varied research priorities, and distinct methodologies. To work through these differences that may arise within inter- and multi-disciplinary research groups, this infographic and accompanying videos aim to:

1. Highlight differences between the “Ways of Understanding”, “Ways of Knowing” and “Ways of Working” across different disciplines
2. Help structure or clarify points in a conversation to overcome the barriers in the different languages of communication and provide a bridge to bring them into dialogue (see Cross-Fertilisation 101).
3. Give prompts, recommendations and examples to create a shared point of departure for fostering collaborative research.

Where do the examples come from?

This document presents examples and concepts from our three-volume book collection on [climate](#), [energy](#), and [mobility](#) policy, which promotes innovative interdisciplinary collaborations. It highlights different perspectives and approaches taken by the contributing authors and offers practical steps for fostering meaningful conversations while addressing potential differences and tensions within these research groups. Additional examples used throughout the text are drawn from a workshop at a virtual symposium organised as part of the book project where at least one member from each chapter team was present, and a survey conducted with the editors of the books.

Disclaimer: This infographic highlights how researchers from different disciplines collaborate around various concepts, such as participatory research, rather than offering detailed instructions on how to carry out participatory research itself.

Cross-Fertilisation 101: A Glossary to Collaborative Knowledge

Boundary object: A concept that helps different groups or cultures communicate and work together, even if they have different ways of understanding or using it.

Cross-fertilisation: This process of integrating knowledge from different disciplines

Epistemology: Where our knowledge comes from

Epistemic community: A group who share knowledge and work together on a specific issue

Epistemic cultures: The different ways in which groups of people, e.g. social scientists or historians, produce, and share knowledge.

Epistemic justice: Recognising everyone’s contributions to knowledge creation

Methodology: The study of methods used to gather, analyze, and interpret knowledge.

Ontology: The way we understand and interpret the world around us

Positionality: Acknowledging that all knowledge is shaped by a specific position or standpoint

Relationality: The idea that beings (humans, and the environment) are interconnected and exist in relationships with one another

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This infographic helps SSH and STEM researchers navigate interdisciplinary challenges and foster dialogue. It highlights cross-fertilisation—integrating knowledge across disciplines—using examples from our three-volume book series on climate, energy, and mobility policy.

1

Ways of...

Understanding

Ontologies shape worldviews: examples include Western science (measurable phenomena) vs. Indigenous perspectives (relational interconnections). These influence policy and problem-solving.

Insight: Recognizing diverse ontologies through cross-fertilisation enhances our capacity to create solutions that respect multiple worldviews.

Knowing

Interdisciplinary collaboration integrates diverse perspectives for innovative solutions. Acknowledging positionality and valuing everyone's contributions to knowledge creation (epistemic justice) enriches knowledge production.

Insight: Cross-fertilisation of knowledge allows for shared understanding across epistemic communities, leading to more comprehensive approaches to sustainability challenges.

Working

Collaboration across disciplines requires overcoming epistemic tensions and finding shared language through continuous negotiation.

Insight: Developing shared methodologies through cross-fertilisation bridges disciplinary divides and supports cohesive teamwork.

2

Navigating Concepts, Definitions, and Topics

Boundary objects like justice, health, and planning connect disciplines despite differing definitions. These concepts foster collaboration by offering shared points of reference (e.g., justice framed through recognition, equity, or trade-offs).

Insight: By using boundary objects, cross-fertilisation helps reconcile diverse viewpoints, creating a foundation for shared goals.

3

Actors

Include **marginalized voices** (e.g., Indigenous communities, women, local stakeholders) for inclusivity and epistemic justice. Representation ensures nuanced perspectives and enriches debates. Consider both traditional and alternative actors, such as NGOs, local authorities, public operators, and citizens.

Insight: Cross-fertilisation ensures diverse voices are integrated into the research design, leading to more inclusive and equitable outcomes.

4

Evidence and Methods

Interdisciplinary research benefits from **mixed methodologies**:

QUANTITATIVE:

Identify patterns, correlations, and trends (e.g., modelling, sampling).

QUALITATIVE:

Provide contextual insights (e.g., ethnography, workshops). Collaborative methods integrate social and technical dimensions, ensuring context-driven and evidence-based solutions.

Insight: Cross-fertilisation of methods enables researchers to address complex challenges with both rigour and context-specific relevance.

Collaborative methods integrate social and technical dimensions, ensuring context-driven and evidence-based solutions.

5

Participation

Genuine participation must avoid being performative. It should **empower all actors**, fostering legitimacy and democratic engagement. Workshops and collaborative efforts bring diverse stakeholders together for meaningful deliberation and innovation.

Insight: Cross-fertilisation of ideas through participatory processes leads to more democratic and impactful outcomes.

6

Policy and Governance

Interdisciplinary approaches align local, national, and EU governance, addressing **multi-level complexities**. Engaging diverse stakeholders ensures equitable and **place-based policies**. Examples include energy justice initiatives and frameworks for sustainable development.

Insight: Cross-fertilisation of governance perspectives facilitates adaptive and inclusive policymaking that reflects diverse needs.

Watch the video by clicking this [link](#) or scanning the QR code

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Ways of...

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Navigating Concepts, Definitions, and Topics

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Concluding Remarks

Blending SSH and STEM methods and conducting inter and multi-disciplinary research not only enriches the problem definition but also integrates technical evaluations with social and policy implications.

The concept of **cross-fertilisation** encourages dialogue across disciplines, fostering richer and more comprehensive knowledge creation by drawing on the unique contributions of each field, it enhances both conceptual and theoretical understanding. Shared concepts like vulnerability, health, or justice act as boundary objects, bridging differences. These ideas are not isolated topics to be studied in silos; rather, they serve as unifying themes that bring together researchers from diverse fields. Methodologically, the use of quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods allows inter- and multidisciplinary teams to produce evidence-based, contextually informed insights. This approach strengthens governance, fostering more innovative, equitable, and effective responses to complex challenges such as climate change, energy transitions, and shifts in mobility.

The inclusion of marginalised voices, especially from Indigenous communities, women, and non-academic knowledge systems, is essential for a more inclusive understanding of climate, energy and mobility issues. Moreover, addressing these imbalances requires both top-down and bottom-up efforts to ensure all voices are heard. However, participation needs to go beyond mere formalities and allow for genuine engagement, where all relevant actors, have a real influence. This can be achieved by creating spaces for open dialogue and collaboration that include diverse perspectives, making the process more democratic and accountable. Eventually, broadening actor representation in policy design can help identify responsibilities for implementation, and provide interventions tailored to place-based needs moving towards transformative policy and governance.

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